

The Trip of Ibn Batalan Al-Baghdadi

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Abstract

Historical studies witnessed a great development in its methodology, as it inspired thinkers of the economic, social and political dimension of theorists, in order to achieve a systematic balance between the present and the present and the assimilation of new common terms between them. The central (Bergs), which emphasized the distribution of the economic side at a time when the administrative boundaries were defined between the economic potential between the cities and their parties, while we find that Ibn Battlan showed us his journey between the countries that the economic disparity between cities, and here we can point out here the state has not appeared. Rather, the term Medina, which is more extensive and comprehensive for freedom of movement, is not visible. There are no borders, and we can consider it (the Arab Islamic countries) as a spatial space in which minds and intellectuals move in search of space to develop their sciences and their economic benefit, and here an important term appears (the globalization of history), according to the theory of growth. The center follows the journey of Ibn Battlan. The economic level of these cities is clear. Flying around the center and we can call it the parties depending on the ease of access, then permission for Ibn Battlan's trip two dimensions, 1 - an economic dimension, 2 - after my.

Introduction

The first requirement is the economic dimension.

The economic dimension is represented by its movement between cities, which we will know by the parties.

In the economic dimension, we find that Ibn Battlan was looking for funding for his research and literature.

Episode divisions of the historical cities of Ibn Battlan's journey.

- A. The commercial and cultural heart of the city (Baghdad)
- B. Transitional area (residential commercial) (Mosul, Diyarbakir, Aleppo)
- C. Workers Residence Area (Egypt)
- D. High-income housing area (Antioch and Constantinople)
- E. The suburban area (Fustat) .

Hence, the theory is clear from a force that explains the impact of the economic uses of the land in creating a kind of (globalization) attraction, especially if we do not know that society at that time period was dependent on the craftsmanship of agriculture and industry, and the time to highlight the cultural and commercial role of

Baghdad and the role of Antakya and Constantinople in providing livelihood opportunities for their East point of contact with the West, this is represented by each of the AB circles).

The cities in the B ring were border cities that depend on trade and are very close to Center-A- represented by Baghdad and the gates represent the trade exchange of north and northwest Baghdad, while the (CE) ring was an area known today as Egypt, which you knew that this was a high-density area of labor because of increase of population, it was.

- 1- It seems to be divided into two regions: Al-Fustat and Taibah, and being a doctor who needs many people for the purpose of practicing his profession, which is far from the competition by the center represented in Baghdad-A- see figure No. -1-.
- 2- The second requirement: (spatial dimension).
- 3- The medical profession needs the presence of a large number of people in order to practice his work, and the distance must be sufficient between the center and the city in which he lived and studied, and here we can notice that the cities in which the distance was less than 1000 km, the period in which he stopped were few, In addition to the fact that these cities are sparsely populated, they are either cities established for a commercial or military purpose, and we clearly note that Ibn Batalan settled in distant cities for several reasons.
- 4- To get rid of the competition.
- 5- There are large numbers of people. Egypt, represented by the city (Al-Fustat), used to provide him with an ideal workplace due to the increase in population and the spread of epidemics such as the plague.
- 6- Batakia settled because it was a city distinguished by its location, the point of contact of the East with the West after its reputation spread and enabled it in this region to practice its profession and improve its economic level, which helped it author books and stability.

Table No. 1-The areas in which Ibn Batalan moved and the distance he traveled

the city name	The distance is km	History	year
Baghdad	-	434AH 1042 AM	-
Mosul	400,05	-	-
Diar Baker	817.2	-	-
Aleppo	1,40,07	437AH	-
Egypt	1489	1048 AM 440 AH	3
Fustat (Egypt)	-	441 AH 1049 AM	-
Constantinople (Istanbul, Turkey)	1610,04	AM1055-1054 447 AH	-
Antakya (southwestern Turkey)	-	-	-
	-	-	-

Source: The researcher's work based on historical book data included in the list of sources.

When applying the simple correlation equation for the cities that he passed through, the correlation force, that is, the interactions of the place becomes clear. It is imposed by the process of spatial settlement because of its proximity to the city of Baghdad, the strength of the link is complete, that is, the chances of practicing his profession in these cities are minimal due to competition.

See Diagram 1- -.

Source: From the researcher's work by relying on Table No. -1-
 While we find the spatial competitor to practice his profession significantly reduced, which is 0.6, and here means he can practice his profession with less competition on average, see Figure 2..
 Figure 2..

Source: From the researcher's work by relying on Table No. -1-
 While we limit that the spatial competition in Egypt was significant as the correlation equation indicates that it is a strong relationship (1) and it is a complete correlation, and for historical accounts, we find that this is identical to it, see Figure -4.
 Figure 4.

Source: From the researcher's work by relying on Table No. -1-

While the factor of spatial competition has become weak in the amount of 0.4 in Constantinople (Turkey Istanbul), this explains to us the reason for its survival in Constantinople and Antakya, because it is far from the spatial competition and in addition to this region is the point where East meets the West. See figure No. -5.

Figure – 5-

Source: From the researcher's work by relying on Table No. -1-

Conclusion :

The historical event has a temporal and spatial dimension, the range of distances, and the movement of the historical event appear and are logically represented by statistical equations.

The analysis of the causes of the movement of Ibn Battlan's physician and his movement between cities at that time of dating has temporal, spatial and economic dimensions governed by historical professional competition factors, and paints us with a picture of the historical time map and the clash of slogans, occupations, services, and the East-West meeting node, the research has determined the strength of the service flow and the interaction of economic benefits The intentions of cultural formation describe to us where we can find the globalization of history, and we know where the forces of cultural attraction for these historical flows lie in a logical quantitative manner and away from the unsupported description with the utmost logic.

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